

DISPLACEMENT FIELD AND STRESS FIELD ANALYSIS OF RADIAL
TIRE CONTACTED WITH ROAD

Wenning Liu Xinwen Du Zhenlong Gu
Research Lab. of Composite Material
Harbin Institute of Technology
Harbin, China

ABSTRACT

Contrary to the traditional tire structure analysis which regards the tire as a shell, this paper takes a radial tire as a complex structure consisting of eleven kinds of materials with 3D finite element method considering both geometrically and physically nonlinear behavior. To verify the computational results, the incandescent light spectra technique was employed to measure to surface displacement field of a tire. Comparison of theoretical and experimental results shows good agreement.

KEYWORDS: Radial/Tire; Nonlinear; Bimodulus; 3D/Finite/Element.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ever since the first automobile tire was manufactured, people continuously tried to improve the tire quality in the past century. However, the tire structure analysis has not yet been solved. In early stage, a tire is simplified as a spring-beam system, a network of rods or a shell[1,2]. Later, with the rapid development of computer and associated numerical computation software, the tire analysis simplify them as a structure made of plated or shells[3,4]. As matter of fact, the deformation along the thickness direction is far from that discribed by Love-Kichhoff assumption.

Fig. 1 shows the materials on various parts of a tire section are different. Every material has its own specific property to achieve the requi overall performance of a tire. The deformation distribution

FIGURE 1. Material Distribution of 165-R-15 Radial Tire

along a line through the thickness is nonhomogeneous, so it is impossible to follow the Love-Kirchhoff assumption. The large displacement leads to geometrical nonlinearity and the rubber material itself is physically nonlinear. With fact's mind, this paper tries to be factual and to find the relation between the properties of various materials and global performance of a tire.

This paper presents the first part of a series of author's research results.

2. BASIC EQUATIONS

According to virtual work principle with large displacement taken into consideration, we have

$$\int_V S_{1j} \delta E_{1j} dv = \int_V p_{0i} \delta u_i dv + \int_{A_{ot}} q_{0i} \delta u_i dA \quad (1)$$

using definition of Green strain

$$E_{1j} = (u_{1,j} + u_{j,1} + u_{k,1} \cdot u_{k,j}) / 2 \quad (2)$$

where

S - Kirchhoff stress

u - displacement vector

p_0 - body force

q_0 - surface force

The equilibrium equation in integral form can be derived from Eq.1.

$$\psi(u) = P(u) + R = 0 \quad (3)$$

where

$$P = \int_V B^T \cdot S dV \quad (4)$$

R is equivalent load and B is transform matrix.

To solve the nonlinear equations thus obtained, the incremental displacement and incremental pressure calculation procedure are employed respectively under loading and inflation. The incremental calculation procedure can also supply intermediate results to the designers. However, the incremental calculation procedure sometimes leads to the significant accumulated error. To remedy this deficiency, Newton-Raphson method is used to improve the computation accuracy. The formular for mth step of incremental method and nth step of Newton-Raphson method can be written as follow:

$$\Delta u_{m+1}^n = - (K_T(u_{m+1}^n))^{-1} \cdot (P(u_{m+1}^n) + \lambda_{m+1} \cdot f_0) \quad (5)$$

$$u_{m+1}^{n+1} = u_{m+1}^n + \Delta u_{m+1}^n \quad (6)$$

where λ_{m+1} is the length of (m+1)th incremental step. f_0 is a given value. K_T is tangent stiffness matrix.

The rubber material is generally considered to be incompressive material and corresponding Poisson ratio is taken to be 0.48-0.49 near 0.50 so as to avoid the irregular of equations. A number of authors wrote the stress-strain relation in the form of strain energy:

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} C_{ij} (I_1 - 3)^i \cdot (I_2 - 3)^j \quad (7)$$

The condition of incompression is

$$I_3 = 1 \quad (8)$$

Here, I_1 , I_2 and I_3 are invariants.

If only the first two terms in Eq.7 is taken, Mooney-Rivlin equation [5] can be gotten:

$$W = C_{10}(I_1 - 3) + C_{01}(I_2 - 3) \quad (9)$$

The properties of the industrial rubber material in tire change with the technological parameters of sulphurization and the volume factor of various additives. They also depend on temperature.

For cord-rubber composite materials, the stiffness ratio of cord and rubber can be as high as 1000, in steel-belt ply, the ratio will still higher even up to 10000. Therefore, the traditional composite laminate theory is no longer applicable. In addition, the material appears to be physically nonlinear and temperature sensitive.

Based on the experimental data obtained by this laboratory [6], the regressive curve can be written as

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = E(\epsilon) * \epsilon \quad (10)$$

where

$$E(\epsilon) = A_0(T) + A_1(T) \cdot \epsilon + A_2(T) \cdot \epsilon^2 + A_3(T) \cdot \epsilon^3 \quad (11)$$

T is temperature, $A_1(T)$ is a function of temperature.

Both rubber material and cord-rubber composite material have different modulus in tension and compression (shown in Fig.2). The compression modulus of rubber is higher than that of tension, $E_c = 30E_t$, and $E_c = E_t/280$ for cord-rubber composite material.

FIGURE 2. Stress - Strain Curve in Tension and compression

For bimodulus material, its stiffness can be written as:

$$C_{ij} = C_{1j}^+ \text{Sg}(f_k(\sigma)) + C_{1j}^- \text{Sg}(-f_k(\sigma)) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\text{Sg}(f_k(\sigma)) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f_k(\sigma) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } f_k(\sigma) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Let $f_k(\sigma) = \sigma_n$ and assume the sign Sg of the moduli to be dominated by cord stress, and the compliance properties of material can be [7]

$$C_{1j}^n = (C_{1j}^{n+} + C_{1j}^{n-}) / 2 \quad (14)$$

with assumption existence of material potential.

3. COMPUTATION

Generally, due to the complexity of tire structure and large number of degree of freedom, computation should be run on a large computer. However, most of the tire plants cannot afford to buy expensive computer. With the situation in mind, the paper tried to develop a computation program which can be implemented on a super microcomputer, especially the front-method is used.

After the incremental nodal loads are determined, input one by one the data of a specific element and calculate its stiffness. Judge every nodal stiffness coefficient whether it will be used in subsequent computation. If it will be no longer used, transfer it to filememory. If it appears for the first time and will be used later, open a new record

for it. If it will be used though it does not appear for the first time then superpose it on relevant record. This procedure will be continued untill all element stiffness are obtained. At this time, all of stiffness coefficients have been stored in file memory. Then, read the data one by one from file memory to solve all of displacements and fixed forces.

4. EXPERIMENT STUDY

To measure the large displacement field for a large object like tire, no relative report is available. The paper adopts incandescent spectra technique to measure 3D large displacement field of tire surface.

On the curve surface of tire, a high reflective light region is inevitable. So the greyness on the picture is not uniform. Care should be taken to ease this problem in order to get satisfactory experiment results.

It should be cared that measure range is directly connected with magnification and tache diameter, therefore, magnification and tache diameter and film resolution should be coordinative.

On the surface of tire, glass beads of 0.30 mm in diameter are sprayed and $f=5.6$, $M=1/10$ are used in the paper.

Fig.3 shows the fringe photograph of pointwise analysis for negative film.

FIGURE 3. Fringe Photograph of Pointwise Analysis

5. RESULT

As an example, a 165-R-15 type radial tire is calculated. Its mesh is shown on Fig.4. In total, it has 2310 nodes and 1870 elements. At first, analysis under inflation is performed, then, the results of inflation analysis is used as the initial condition of performing analysis under loading.

Fig.5—Fig.7 show the computation results of surface displacement of 3 sections (0 degree, 90 degree and 180 degree section) in the tire which has 20mm maximum vertical displacement. In those figures, black triangle

FIGURE 4. F.E.M. Mesh of Tire in a section and Circum

FIGURE 5. Displacement of 0 Degerr Section
0.2MPa Pressure. 20mm Contact Vertical Disp.

FIGURE 6. Displacement of 90 Degerr Section
0.2MPa Pressure, 20mm Contact Vertical Disp.

FIGURE 7. Displacement of 180 Degerr Section
0.2MPa Pressure, 20mm Contact Vertical Disp.

FIGURE 8. Cord-1 Stress of Various Section along the Meridian
0.2MPa Pressure, 20mm Contact Vertical Displacement.

FIGURE 9. Cord-2 Stress of Various Section along the Meridian
0.2MPa Pressure, 20mm Contact Vertical Displacement.

represents experimental result. Fig.8—Fig.10 show the stress field in two cord rubber ply and one steel-belt ply along the meridian. It can be noted that the effect of loading on steel-belt ply is larger than that on cord-rubber ply, and the effect on steel-belt depresses rapidly when section is out from the contact field. Fig. 11 gives the vertical displacement curve of outer side in 3 sections (0 degree,90 degree and 180 degree section). In the figure, black triangle represents the experimental result.

6. CONCLUSION

- (1). 3D FEM is necessary in order to obtain the real displacement of a tire under loading.
- (2). The nonlinearity due to large displacement and material properties makes the problem very complicated. The incremental calculation procedure associated with Newton-Raphson method yields satisfactory results for nonlinear analysis.
- (3). The incandescent spectra technique is a feasible means to measure the 3D displacement field on the tire surface.

REFERENCE

- [1] Brewer, H.K., Tire Science and Technology, Vol.1, No.1, 47(1973)
- [2] Takashi Akasaka and Kaznyuki kabe, Tire Sci. Techn., Vol.5, No.4 171 (1977).
- [3] Satyamurthy, K and Hirschfeldt, I.R., Tire Sci. Techn., Vol.15, No.2, 97(1987).
- [4] Patel, H.P. and Zorowrki, C.F., Tive Sci. Techn., Vol.6, No. 4, 233(1978).
- [5] Walter, J.D., Rubber chem. Techn., 51, 524(1978)
- [6] Xingwen, D. and Jinyu, J., Ninth Annual Meeting of Tire Society, America, 1990.
- [7] Zhenlong, G. and Lan, M., J. Com. Mat., 23: 988-996(1989).

BIOGRAPH

My name is Wenning Liu. I was born in Liaoning province, northeast of China, in Feb. 8, 1964. I passed the entrance examination of Jilin University and studied in department of mathematics for four years, and graduated in 1984, in same year, entered to Harbin Institute of Technology to study about computation mechanics for Master Degree, in 1987. I began to research composite material mechanics for ph. D. and laid main emphasis on bi-nonlinear and bi-modulus composite material structure, and finished the ph. D dissertation in 1990. Now, I'm working about dynamic response of aviation tire as a past doctor in Nanjing Aeronautical Institute.

